

MEDICAL SCIENCES

MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING OF THE SPHENOID SINUS AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN NEUROSURGERY

Bechev K.

*Department of Neurosurgery, University Hospital "Pulmed";
Department of General and Clinical Pathology, Faculty of Medicine, Medical University – Plovdiv*

Abstract

In neurosurgical practice, six main types of sinus are recognised: sphenoid body type, lateral type, clival type, lesser wing type, anterior type and combined type. The pneumatization of the sinus and its intermediate septa, as well as the presence of a double wall in the form of a connective tissue membrane located on the dorsal wall of the sphenoid sinus, are of great importance. The aim of this study is to show the importance of the size and type of the sphenoid sinus based on MRI examinations. As the width of the sphenoid sinus increases, so does the distance between the two carotid arteries. This difference is statistically significant and reliable in the study group, with a confidence interval of $p < 0.05$. These data are important for planning surgical access to the sellar and parasellar regions.

Keywords: sphenoid sinus, magnetic resonance imaging of the brain, transsphenoidal access, morphology of the sphenoid sinus, anatomical variations.

Introduction

This study enabled us to confirm the literature data and to classify the types of sphenoid sinus into six main groups: sphenoid body type, lateral type, clival type, lesser wing type, anterior type, and combined type [1, 3, 4] Magnetic resonance imaging of the brain provides information regarding the location of the tumour in relation to the normal anatomical structures in this area. The width of the sphenoid sinus is of key importance, as it allows for preoperative planning of bone trepanation of the sinus and avoidance of iatrogenic damage to the carotid artery [3,4] In this study, we demonstrated a correlation between the width of the sphenoid sinus and the intercarotid distance. MRI images of the skull base have become the standard in preoperative preparation for patients with tumours and inflammatory diseases in the SS and pituitary region.

Materials and methods

I present coronal sections in T2 projections from 112 magnetic resonance imaging scans of the brain performed in the Neurosurgery Department of the Plovdiv University Hospital 'Pulmed' for the period 2023–2024. Two groups of patients participated in the study: men and women. The study includes two groups of patients: men and women. The average age of the men is 50.97, and that of the women is 47.83. The images show the detailed anatomy of the sphenoid sinus and

the pituitary region. Measurements of the width of the sphenoid sinus, chiasma opticum and intracarotid distance were made using two image visualisation programmes, RadiAnt and Weasis. The measurements were made only in the coronal plane of T2 projections from brain MRI. The inclusion criteria were: presence of coronal sections in the study, Bulgarian population, normal morphology of the structures in the area of interest, which does not exclude the types of sphenoid sinus. Figure 1 shows coronal sections through the intercavernous space, the chiasm and the sphenoid sinus. The aim of this study is to prove the relationship between the width of the sphenoid sinus and the intercarotid space, as this relationship is of important clinical significance in transsphenoidal surgical approaches to the skull base. Statistical analysis, including t-tests to compare measurements between the two groups and correlation to examine the relationship between SS dimensions and intercarotid distance, was performed using R software (The R Core Team, R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria). The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to assess the normality of the data before further statistical analyses were performed. Descriptive statistics, such as mean and standard deviation, were calculated to summarise the measurements of the analysed structures.

Figure 1 (A and B). MRI image of the brain (coronal section in T2 sequence). Panel A shows the width of the chiasma opticum and the intercarilage space. Panel B shows the width of the sphenoid sinus, the median septum and the asymmetry between the two parts of the SS.

RESULTS

The average age of participants was 49.1 years (95% CI: 45.6–52.5). The Shapiro-Wilk test for normality yielded a p-value of 0.033, indicating a deviation from normal distribution. In terms of gender distribution, 40.2% of participants were male. Measurements of anatomical structures showed a mean intercarotid space width of 16.830 mm (95% CI: 16.051 - 17.609) with a standard deviation of 4.161. The Shapiro-Wilk test showed a normal distribution ($p = 0.350$). The width of the optic chiasm was 13.063 mm on average (95% CI: 12.717 - 13.408). Similar to the distribution in men, the Shapiro-Wilk test showed abnormality ($p < 0.001$). The SS width (SSW) was measured at an average of 28.366 mm (95% CI: 27.759 - 28.973). We also conducted t-tests for independent samples to examine potential gender differences in the main anatomical sections among the study participants. The age distribution between the gender groups showed no statistically significant differences ($t = -0.911$, $df = 110$, $p = 0.364$), suggesting similar age profiles across genders in the study cohort. Similarly, anatomical measurements such as intercarotid space width, optic chiasm width, and SSW did not show significant differences between the sexes. Intercarotid space width showed a mean difference of 1.508 cm ($p = 0.134$), the width of the optic chiasm had a mean difference of -0.749 mm

($p = 0.456$), and the SSW had a mean difference of -0.268 mm ($p = 0.789$). These results suggest that anatomical differences in these structures do not differ significantly between men and women in the study population. Effect sizes (Cohen's d) were calculated to quantify the practical significance of these differences. The effect ranged from very small (Cohen's $d = -0.0516$ for SSW) to moderate (Cohen's $d = 0.2906$ for intercarotid space), indicating minimal to moderate practical significance of the observed parameters. The width of the intercarotid space and SSW show a statistically significant positive correlation (Spearman's $\rho = 0.292$, $p = 0.002$), indicating that individuals with wider SS tend to have a larger intercarotid space. The correlations between the width of the optic chiasm and the other variables (intercarotid space, SSW, age) are insignificant, suggesting that the dimensions of the optic chiasm do not correlate with these anatomical areas or with age within the studied population. Age shows a weak negative correlation with intercarotid space width (Spearman's $\rho = -0.109$, $p = 0.252$) and SSW (Spearman's $\rho = -0.072$, $p = 0.453$), although these are not statistically significant. This indicates that age may have a minimal effect on intercarotid space or SSW dimensions in this cohort. The results are presented graphically in Figure 2.

Correlation between intercarotid space and sphenoid sinus width coronal plane (mm)

$S = 1.66e+05$, $p = 1.81e-03$, $\hat{\rho}_{\text{spearman}} = 0.29$, $CI_{95\%} [0.11, 0.46]$, $n_{\text{pairs}} = 112$

Figure 2. Shows the relationship between SSW and intracarotid distance.

Discussion

The sphenoid bone is located in the middle of the skull base. The body, corpus ossis sphenoidalis, is the central part of the bone. Its upper surface is slightly concave and forms the sella turcica. It consists of a central fossa, fossa hypophysialis, bounded anteriorly by the tuberculum sellae and posteriorly by the dorsum sellae with paired processes, processus clinoides anterior et posterior. To the sides of the sella turcica are the carotid sulcus and the lingula sphenoidalis, and in front of the tuberculum sellae is the prechiasmatic sulcus, which extends laterally to the optic canal. The posterior surface of the body fuses with the pars basilaris of the occipital bone and forms the posterior part of the skull base. The anterior surface of the body surrounds the nasal cavity. In childhood, the entrance to the sphenoid sinus is narrowed by a triangular-shaped bone lamella [2, 3, 4, 5].

Based on this classification, Hardy and colleagues have developed a standard for access to the sella region. Wang and Bidari divide the most common sellar type into: 1. Sphenoid body type – pneumatization does not extend beyond the body of the sphenoid bone; 2. Lateral type – the sinus extends laterally; 3. Clival type – expansion of the sinus backwards towards the clivus; 4. Lesser wing type – pneumatization extends to the lesser wings; 5. Anterior type – the cavity extends anteriorly; 6. Combined type – a combination of the other types [3,7]. Over the years, various authors have measured the sphenoid sinus (SS). The team of Gulgun Kayalioglu MD et al. Found the following dimensions in bone, cadaver and MRI images: length in the upper part of the sinus – 13.51 +/- 3.25 mm; length in the lower part of the sinus – 24.57 +/- 6.65 mm; height in the anterior part of the sinus – 21.27 +/- 4.25 mm; height in the posterior part of the sinus – 14.5 +/- 4.07 mm [8]. Many other authors in the world literature have studied SS and its significance for neurosurgical practice, but to date there are no published clinical studies on this topic in Bulgaria, making this study the first for the country. Primary malignant tumours of the sphenoid sinus vary from 1 to 2% of sinus tumours according to literature data. The sinus can also be a site of secondary

metastases from tumours of the mammary gland, lungs, kidneys, thyroid gland or prostate [6, 8].

SS has a highly variable septal and cavity architecture. Accurate preoperative diagnosis is necessary to avoid potential complications, including haemorrhages and other serious problems. The degree and type of SS pneumatization play an important role in providing different surgical access to specific structures. Preoperative CT of the head and MRI of the pituitary region are of great importance in determining the unique anatomy of each individual patient and outlining the path of the respective surgical access [9].

Conclusion

The sphenoid sinus is an important corridor for reaching pathological processes located in the sellar and parasellar regions. Knowledge of the anatomical structure and variations in the latter is crucial when planning surgical interventions. MRI of the brain provides detailed information about the types of sphenoid sinus, its width, and its relationship to the carotid artery, the chiasm, and the pituitary gland. This allows for a good preoperative plan to be made regarding the volume of trepanation of the sphenoid sinus without causing iatrogenic trauma to the intact nerve structures.

References

1. Abuzayed B, Tanriöver N, Ozlen F, Gazioglu N, Ulu MO, Kafadar AM, Eraslan B, Akar Z. (2009) Endoscopic endonasal transsphenoidal approach to the sellar region: results of endoscopic dissection on 30 cadavers. *Turk Neurosurg.* Jul;19(3):237-44.
2. Yamashita S, Resende LA, Trindade AP, Zanini MA (2014). A radiologic morphometric study of sellar, infrassellar and parasellar regions by magnetic resonance in adults. *Springerplus.* doi: 10.1186/2193-1801-3-291.
3. Wang J, Bidari S, Inoue K, Yang H, Rhoton A Jr (210). Extensions of the sphenoid sinus: a new classification. *Neurosurgery,* doi: 10.1227/01.NEU.0000367619.24800.B1.
4. Sethi KS, Choudhary S, Ganesan PK, Sood N, Basil R, Dhawan S (2023). Sphenoid sinus anatomical

variants and pathologies: pictorial essay. *Neuroradiology*, 65(8): pp.1187-1203. doi: 10.1007/s00234-023-03163-4.

5. Agam, Matthew S BS; Zada, Gabriel MD (2018). Complications Associated With Transsphenoidal Pituitary Surgery: Review of the Literature. *Neurosurgery* 65 (CN_suppl_1):pp 69-73, DOI: 10.1093/neuros/nyy160

6. Darouassi Y, Chihani M, Touati MM, Nadour K, Ammar H, Bouaity B (2014) Adenocarcinoma of the sphenoid sinus. *Pan Afr Med J.* 18:284. doi: 10.11604/pamj.2014.18.284.4416.

7. Karpishchenko S, Arustamyan I, Stancheva O, Sharko K, Kaplun D, Bogachev MI (2020). Intraopera-

tive Sphenoid Sinus Volume Measurement as an Alternative Technique to Intraoperative Computer Tomography. *Diagnostics (Basel)*, 10(6):350. doi: 10.3390/diagnostics10060350.

8. Kayalioglu G, Erturk M, Varol T (2005). Variations in sphenoid sinus anatomy with special emphasis on pneumatization and endoscopic anatomic distances. *Neurosciences (Riyadh)*. 10(1): pp.79-84.

9. Yan S, Huang S, Wu Z, Liu Y, Men Y, Nie X, Guo J (2023) A CBCT Investigation of the Sella Turcica Dimension and Sella Turcica Bridging in Different Vertical Growth Patterns. *J Clin Med.* 12(5):1890. doi: 10.3390/jcm12051890.